

Towards Sustainable 6G Compute Continuum: Energy-aware Zero-Touch Network and Service Management used for Dynamic Vehicular Service Deployments

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Abstract—The exponential growth in connectivity and computing demand has made Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure (NFVI) a major contributor to global energy consumption. Conventional network and service deployments, whether based on legacy hardware appliances or NFVI stacks, struggle to dynamically provision resources for peak data traffic demand. This results in nearly constant energy consumption, even during low-traffic periods, leading to inefficient resource use. Network softwarization and virtualization have enabled flexible and programmable service deployments, which are beneficial for the rapid and dynamic scaling of network functions. This paper validates energy-aware service and network orchestration with a Zero-touch Network and Service Management (ZSM) framework for the autonomous optimization of computing, network, and power resources from NFVI in a use case focused on connected mobility, and in particular, smart traffic management. By modeling road traffic based on vehicle count and type and 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) profiles for data formats in vehicular communication scenarios, the ZSM framework adjusts services and resources to service requirements and to actual demand. Experimental validation on the real-life Smart Highway testbed in Antwerp, Belgium, demonstrates a strong correlation between vehicular traffic and power consumption, supporting the hypothesis that adaptive compute and network resource management reduces unnecessary energy use and advances the vision of sustainable and self-optimizing Sixth-Generation (6G) networks.

Index Terms—Zero-Touch Management, Energy Efficiency, 6G, Vehicular Networks, Smart Highway, Sustainability, Edge Computing

I. INTRODUCTION

Information and communication technologies already represent a significant share of global energy consumption, with network infrastructures such as radio access nodes, roadside units, and distributed computing devices contributing heavily to this demand [1]. The growing complexity of these infrastructures has resulted in unprecedented energy use across both network and computing domains, as radio stations, switches, servers, and virtualized functions continuously consume power, even during periods of low traffic [2]. In the context of Sixth-Generation (6G) networks, sustainability has emerged as a fundamental design objective alongside capacity, latency, and reliability [3].

Current network infrastructures typically rely on static configurations that allocate fixed computational and

communication resources regardless of actual demand [4]. The power consumption of communication and computing resources remains almost constant, even when the traffic load decreases, resulting in substantial energy waste. The central hypothesis of this work is that re-configuring network segments dynamically according to real-time traffic demand enables adaptive power consumption and significantly reduces energy use during low-demand periods.

Intelligent resource and service orchestration can optimize resource allocation to improve efficiency and energy awareness while maintaining strict quality of service for mission-critical verticals such as vehicular communications [5,6]. Zero-touch Network and Service Management (ZSM) has emerged as a paradigm that reduces human intervention toward autonomous network systems capable of self-optimization [7]. By continuously monitoring correlated metrics such as End-to-End (E2E) latency and CPU utilization and making decisions, ZSM can adapt computing and network resources with reference to data traffic demand fluctuations [8]. To achieve truly ZSM, it is essential to obtain autonomous control, cross-domain data analytics, and proactive decision-making [9].

This study addresses the challenge of energy-aware autonomy in service and network management. To evaluate the performance of this energy-aware ZSM framework, we focus on dynamic vehicular systems and vehicular services consuming Fifth-Generation (5G) network and compute infrastructure. Highways offer an ideal platform for experimentation through an available smart highway testbed, allowing real-world validation of adaptive resource management strategies. In this context, highways are considered a strategic environment for experimentation, as they concentrate large numbers of users and communication devices, resulting in significant energy consumption. For instance, if an increased number of vehicles is connected to a Roadside Unit (RSU), consuming vehicular edge services, the CPU load is expected to increase along with power consumption.

Fig. 1. Modularity of the ZSM framework: heterogeneous KPI collection and processing.

To this end, we present a ZSM framework (Figure 1) that processes heterogeneous metrics from the Network Function Virtualization Infrastructure (NFVI), including E2E latency, CPU, and power consumption, and makes priority-based decisions to scale services according to demand. The framework enables energy-aware closed-loop orchestration of network and computing resources across eight RSUs deployed on the Smart Highway (E313, Antwerp), as shown in Figure 2. Each RSU collects Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) such as CPU utilization, latency, and power consumption, while traffic sensors provide vehicle counts and types for each highway segment. To validate the performance of the proposed ZSM framework, the demand indicators derived from inductive loop sensors are used for experimental purposes to emulate realistic load conditions on the Smart Highway testbed.

II. ENERGY-AWARENESS IN NETWORK SOFTWAREZATION

Power monitoring across the computing continuum, such as edge/Multi-Access Edge Computing (MEC) nodes and cloud, is a prerequisite for any energy-aware orchestration [10]. In virtualized environments and NFVI stacks, power is consumed by multiple layers, including the physical platform (CPU sockets, memory, disks), platform firmware and fans, the hypervisor or container runtime, and the hosted Virtual Machine (VM)/container instances [11]. With the ongoing softwarization of networks, where virtually all network functions are deployed as microservices in containerized form on top of the NFVI, monitoring power consumption across the compute continuum becomes essential to capture the true energy footprint of service execution. Accurate observability, therefore, requires combining direct electrical measurements with platform and software telemetry [12].

A. Energy-aware solutions in network management

Power consumption monitoring in the computing continuum of networks is a critical enabler for optimizing

Fig. 2. Live dashboard map from the ZSM framework GUI, displaying RSU locations along the Smart Highway and their respective paired inductive sensors for vehicular traffic monitoring.

energy efficiency and sustainability. For example, Daryathna et al. [10] provide a comprehensive survey of data center energy consumption modeling, highlighting that servers can account for up to 26% of total data center power use, while network equipment typically contributes 10–20%. In the context of virtualized network functions, Kar et al. [9] and Liu et al. [11] propose dynamic placement and orchestration strategies that rely on accurate power models derived from both hardware sensors and virtualization layer telemetry. These approaches enable the identification of energy hotspots and support adaptive resource allocation to minimize overall consumption. Collectively, these works establish the foundation for energy-aware management in modern networked and virtualized infrastructures.

Energy-aware solutions in network management have evolved to address the growing need to reduce energy consumption while maintaining service quality and performance. Early approaches focused on dynamic resource allocation and traffic engineering to adapt network capacity to real-time demand, thereby minimizing idle power usage [1]. Techniques such as sleep modes for idle devices, energy-efficient protocols, and adaptive routing have been shown to significantly reduce the energy footprint of both wired and wireless networks [13].

In virtualized and cloud environments, orchestration frameworks leverage machine learning and optimization algorithms to dynamically scale resources, migrate workloads, and consolidate services, further enhancing energy efficiency. For example, Rawat et al. [1] demonstrated that Software Defined Networking (SDN) can reduce energy consumption and carbon emissions by enabling fine-grained control over network flows and device states. In mobile and Radio Access Network (RAN), advanced sleep modes and reinforcement learning-based controllers have been proposed to optimize energy use without compromising quality of service [4]. Recent studies report that energy-aware management strategies can yield energy savings of up to 30% in mobile networks under realistic workloads [3].

B. ZSM for energy-aware solutions

ZSM has emerged as a transformative paradigm for autonomous, closed-loop network and service management in next-generation infrastructures [7]. While the standard does not inherently address energy-awareness, our work extends the paradigm by embedding energy as a first-class objective. Barrachina-Muñoz et al. [8] provide an experimental assessment of ZSM in Beyond 5G (B5G) networks, demonstrating that zero-touch orchestration can achieve scalable, efficient management of network slices and resources. Ocampo et al. [14] propose reinforcement learning-driven service placement across the compute continuum in 6G networks, showing that intelligent orchestration can adapt to heterogeneous environments and fluctuating workloads. These approaches enable the network to autonomously adjust service configurations, migrate workloads, and activate energy-saving modes in response to real-time demand and performance metrics.

Vehicular vertical services such as autonomous, tele-operated, and assisted driving rely on the compute continuum, where functions are dynamically placed across the cloud, edge, and RSUs to meet stringent latency and reliability requirements. We target highways as critical environments where dense concentrations of users and devices make energy consumption particularly relevant, and vehicular dynamics create highly variable demand patterns. To address this, the proposed framework tackles energy overprovisioning by aligning orchestration decisions with realistic traffic-driven demand rather than static configurations or synthetic models.

The KPI set of the ZSM framework is extended beyond internal telemetry to include external vehicular traffic data, mapped from inductive loop sensors to RSU locations and ingested into the analytics module through a preliminary mapper. This integration highlights the KPI-agnostic nature of the framework, which bases decisions on prioritized requirements: ultra-low E2E latency for safety-critical maneuvers, bounded energy consumption to prevent overprovisioning, and sufficient computational capacity to sustain service continuity under fluctuating traffic loads.

Together, these elements bridge the gap between theoretical energy-aware orchestration and validation in realistic, traffic-driven vehicular scenarios. Specifically, this paper advances a ZSM framework with energy-awareness capabilities that autonomously balances service placement, scaling, and migration across the 6G compute continuum. By jointly prioritizing latency and energy, the framework ensures Quality of Service (QoS) compliance while avoiding unnecessary energy use. Its detailed design is presented in Section III, with validation on real highway traffic data in Section IV.

Fig. 3. Modularity of the ZSM framework by the extension of KPI metrics with vehicular traffic counts in the Smart Highway testbed.

III. FRAMEWORK DESIGN AND EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

This section introduces the experimental foundation of our work and the framework built upon it. We first describe the Smart Highway testbed to establish the real-world environment in which our approach is validated, and then we detail the proposed orchestration framework and its traffic-driven demand modeling to show how it operates under realistic conditions.

A. The Smart Highway testbed capabilities

The Smart Highway, displayed in Figure 2, is a large-scale, real-world experimental platform designed to support the development and validation of advanced vehicular and networked services. Located along a four-kilometer section of the E313 highway in Antwerp, Belgium, the testbed is publicly documented and accessible for research collaboration¹. It has been specifically designed to enable experimentation in distributed and edge environments, vehicular communications, and orchestration frameworks under realistic traffic conditions.

The infrastructure currently comprises eight RSUs deployed along the monitored highway segment, each equipped with computing-capable units that host containerized applications. Each RSU integrates the following components: radio and antenna units supporting wireless communications, General Purpose Computing Units (GPCUs), a power control unit for energy distribution and monitoring across RSU components, and remote access functionality for the management and configuration of deployed setups.

In addition to the fixed infrastructure, a On-board Unit (OBU) is used as a mobile test unit. Specifically, a BMW X5 xDrive25d LO is equipped with similar appliances as the RSUs and acts as a testing vehicle that connects to edge vertical services deployed on RSUs. This setup enables the generation of realistic application traffic

¹Smart Highway testbed: <https://www.fed4fire.eu/testbeds/smart-highway/>

for the evaluation of E2E latency under real driving conditions, a capability that is fundamental for assessing the performance of vehicular services. Network and vehicular service monitoring, stress testing, orchestration, and data collection are executed as containerized services managed through Kubernetes (K8s), ensuring the flexibility, scalability, and reproducibility of experiments.

B. Proposed Framework

The proposed ZSM framework is implemented and validated on the Smart Highway testbed, with eight RSUs as distributed edge nodes. Each RSU hosts containerized services managed by K8s and is instrumented to provide continuous monitoring of heterogeneous KPIs, including CPU utilization, memory usage, E2E latency, and power consumption. These measurements form the basis of a closed-loop orchestration cycle in which the framework observes system behavior, analyzes demand, and enforces orchestration decisions in near real-time.

E2E latency is critical for safety-related vehicular services because warnings and control decisions must arrive within tens of milliseconds to be actionable at highway speeds; otherwise, the braking/avoidance window closes. Under these bounds, we treat E2E latency as a first-class KPI alongside energy. In addition, OBU units mounted in test vehicles generate realistic application traffic by sending probe requests to services hosted on the RSUs. Each probe is timestamped at the OBU before transmission and again at the service endpoint upon reception. With time-synchronized clocks across OBUs, RSUs, and edge servers, the framework derives one-way and round-trip latency under real driving conditions, thereby enriching the KPIs set with field-validated metrics.

Energy consumption is monitored through a multi-source pipeline. At the RSUs, managed Power Distribution Units (PDUs) provide per-device and aggregate electrical measurements accessible via Simple Network Management Protocol (SNMP). These readings are complemented by platform telemetry (e.g., Running Average Power Limit (RAPL), Intelligent Platform Management Interface (IPMI)). The orchestration logic aggregates these KPIs and traffic analytics into a continuous control loop. At its core lies a decision-making engine that evaluates multiple objectives simultaneously through a Multi-Criteria Decision-Making (MCDM) process, treating energy consumption as a first-class KPI alongside E2E latency. Configurable weights are assigned to each telemetry KPI, derived from predefined priorities that reflect the operational goals of the monitored NFVI.

The decision engine determines whether to migrate services between RSUs, scale compute resources up or down, instantiate or stop service instances, or activate and deactivate network functions. Once decisions are

made, they are enforced automatically through K8s Application Programmable Interfaces (APIs), which manage the life cycle of containerized services at the RSUs. This ensures a zero-touch orchestration process where monitoring, analysis, decision-making, and control are performed in closed-loop processes in near real-time.

C. Traffic-Based Demand Modeling

A key element of the proposed framework is the integration of live vehicular traffic analytics into the orchestration cycle. Vehicular statistics are collected from inductive detection loop sensors deployed along Flemish highways. These sensors, operated by the regional Roads and Traffic Agency² and supplemented by the Flemish Traffic Centre³, provide vehicle counts every 60 seconds, distinguishing between different classes of vehicles, such as passenger cars, trucks, and buses. Each RSU in the Smart Highway testbed is geographically paired with specific inductive loop sensors due to their physical proximity, as illustrated in Figure 2. This spatial correlation enables the direct mapping of sensor data to the RSU locations, ensuring that the number and type of vehicles passing through a given highway segment can be associated with the corresponding edge node.

Within the ZSM framework, this mapping process transforms raw traffic counts into actionable demand indicators, as displayed in Figure 3. The estimated traffic demand (request rate and data throughput) can be derived per segment by aligning vehicle density and type distribution with 3rd Generation Partnership Project (3GPP) TS 22.186 V2X use-case traffic profiles such as Advanced Driving, Platooning, Extended Sensors, or Remote Driving [5] and 5G Media Streaming profiles [6]. These demand estimates are then incorporated into the closed-loop orchestration cycle, where they are evaluated alongside system KPIs such as CPU utilization, latency, and power consumption. In this way, live traffic analytics are directly linked to orchestration decisions, enabling the framework to anticipate demand fluctuations and adjust computing and network resources proportionally.

This integration of inductive sensor data with RSU monitoring establishes the foundation for energy-aware orchestration. As vehicles pass by each highway segment, their presence and type are registered by the inductive sensors and mapped to the corresponding RSU. When vehicles connect to edge services for vehicular applications, the RSU experiences increased CPU load and network activity, which in turn raises its power consumption. By correlating vehicle counts and types with system metrics such as CPU utilization and power usage, the framework can dynamically adjust resource allocation to match real demand. The actual use of these

²Roads and Traffic Agency: <https://www.wegenenverkeer.be/>

³The Flemish Traffic Centre: <https://www.verkeerscentrum.be/>

demand indicators to emulate load and stress-test the RSUs is presented in Section IV, where their impact on orchestration decisions and energy consumption is evaluated.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the experimental validation of the proposed ZSM framework on the Smart Highway testbed. We evaluate the performance of our ZSM framework using real-world vehicular traffic data to emulate realistic load conditions and discuss the implications of our findings for energy-aware network management.

A. Real-world vehicular traffic data for validation tests

To validate the performance of the proposed ZSM framework, we leverage real vehicular traffic data collected from inductive loop sensors on the Smart Highway testbed. These measurements provide the number and type of vehicles per aggregation window (60 seconds), which are then translated into synthetic service requests directed at the RSUs. The goal is to emulate realistic and dynamic load conditions that reflect actual vehicular activity. The mapping procedure follows a profile-based approach. Each detected vehicle is associated with a service profile derived from 3GPP traffic specification profiles that define representative traffic patterns, such as video streaming, sensor sharing, and control and safety messages [5,6].

The 3GPP service profiles are used here primarily as reference models to guide the mapping procedure and ensure alignment with standardized traffic categories. For the purpose of this experimental validation, we implemented a simplified request format corresponding to the best-effort infotainment profile. The server-side application is instantiated as a containerized service on the RSUs acting as distributed edge nodes, ensuring proximity to the vehicles. These service instances can be accessed via the wireless interfaces of the RSUs. This setup enables low-latency access to infotainment services while allowing the ZSM framework to dynamically scale or migrate instances in response to traffic-driven demand. This choice allowed us to generate reproducible load conditions that still capture the essential dynamics of vehicular traffic, while leaving the integration of additional service categories (e.g., safety-critical or cooperative perception flows) for future work.

For each vehicle, the scheduler instantiates a request generator according to the corresponding service profile. The number of requests per vehicle and their intensity are therefore not constant but depend on the selected profile. For example, a vehicle mapped to the video streaming profile [6] generates sustained high-rate requests, while one mapped to the control-message profile generates frequent but lightweight packets. This ensures that the aggregate demand at each RSU reflects both the density

TABLE I
LATENCY AND POWER MEASUREMENTS FOR NODES FROM THE ZSM ORCHESTRATOR.

Node	E2E latency (ms)	Power (W)	Time (hh:mm:ss)
rsu1	90	59	00:37:51
rsu1	90	59	00:37:51
rsu1	90	61	00:37:51
rsu1	90	61	00:37:51
rsu5	102	51	00:37:52
rsu5	93	51	00:37:52
rsu5	93	51	00:37:52

Fig. 4. Correlation between vehicular traffic, power consumption, CPU load, and E2E latency.

and the composition of the vehicular flow. By continuously adapting the mix of requests to the observed traffic composition, the scheduler emulates realistic demand fluctuations. These fluctuations are monitored by the ZSM framework.

B. Evaluation

The ZSM framework employs MCDM techniques, enabling the orchestrator to evaluate and act upon multiple heterogeneous indicators, such as E2E latency and power consumption, simultaneously. Each indicator is assigned a specific priority and weight, reflecting its importance in the overall orchestration strategy. By processing these diverse metrics together, the orchestrator can make balanced decisions that optimize resource allocation and service quality, even when the indicators have different units, scales, or operational impacts. This approach ensures that the system adapts dynamically to changing conditions while respecting the predefined priorities of each criterion.

In the vehicular mobility scenario, the ZSM framework orchestrates resources through a hierarchical decision process. Candidate nodes are first ranked by their E2E latency, with only those meeting the service requirements considered. To avoid unnecessary redeployments, nodes with latency differences below 30 ms are treated as equivalent. Among these, the orchestrator then selects the node with the lowest power consumption, thereby minimizing energy usage while preserving service quality. Table I illustrates representative decisions, showing how the framework balances latency and energy efficiency in practice.

Prior to integrating the vehicular traffic-based demand model, power consumption values remained nearly constant despite significant fluctuations in traffic. After incorporating real-world traffic data into the orchestration process, the framework enables adaptive resource management, allowing power consumption to better reflect actual demand. This effect is illustrated in Figure 4 after 00:35 hours, where power usage begins to vary in response to traffic-driven emulated loads. These results further demonstrate the value of onboarding external KPIs, as described earlier, to enhance the orchestrator's ability to make energy-aware decisions.

C. Future Research Directions

Future research will extend the current framework by integrating Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning (AI/ML)-based predictive analytics to anticipate traffic variations and proactively adjust resources. The inclusion of external analytics platforms will enable richer contextual awareness and multi-domain coordination. Additional experiments will evaluate the scalability of the model in denser or urban environments beyond highways. Ultimately, the project seeks to establish a fully autonomous, energy-optimized management system capable of real-time adaptation across heterogeneous 6G infrastructures.

V. CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we presented an energy-aware ZSM framework for vehicular networks, validated on the Smart Highway testbed. By integrating real-time vehicular data with KPI-driven orchestration and adaptive scaling, the framework predicts data request rates based on vehicle types and counts, enabling efficient resource allocation and reducing unnecessary energy provisioning. Preliminary results confirm the feasibility of this approach, demonstrating its potential to promote the sustainable and efficient use of computing and communication resources. This contribution advances the realization of self-optimizing and environmentally responsible 6G networks, while future work will refine the demand model and extend validation through large-scale, real-world experiments.

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